

FAN, TA'LIM, MADANIYAT VA INNOVATSIYA

[Jild: 03 Nashr: 7 (2024)] ISSN: 2992-8915

www.mudarrisziyo.uz

THE EFFECT OF GOVERNANCE ON THE ECONOMIC GROWTH AND EXPORT FLOW OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: Transparent, participative, inclusive, and responsive management of public affairs are hallmarks of good governance, which also encompasses the norms, values, and rules of the game by which such management is carried out. Therefore, governance might be subtle and hard to detect. Governance, in its broadest meaning, refers to the social and institutional framework that facilitates people's and stakeholders' engagement with and influence over the government. It goes beyond just the traditional governmental structures.

Exports play a crucial role in economic development, serving as a major driver of national progress and prosperity. The capacity of nations to effectively engage in international trade and capitalize on export opportunities is influenced by a variety of factors, among which governance stands out as a critical factor.

The present research contributes to society by shedding light on the significance of governance in relation to international commerce and financial development

Keywords: GDP per capita, Governance, Export, International Trade.

Data source

The data provided in this thesis research covers a period of 20 years from 2001 to 2020, and the data was collected from four dataset websites, which are the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTADSTAT), World Bank Indicators, The State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan Statistics (stat.uz), and Research and Expertise on the World Economy (CEPII).

Figure 1: Correlation between log value of GDP per capita and governance index.

Source: Done in Stata based on above mentioned databases.

It may be observed the relationship between GDP per capita value and governance index by looking at the scatter plot in Figure 1. In addition, this graph was also created by taking the GDP per capita value of 105 nations and comparing it to their governance index between the years 2001 and 2020. The log value of GDP per capita and governance indicators are described correspondingly on the y axis and the x axis in this graph. According to the graph, the red line is demonstrating an increasing tendency, hence, we are able to state that an increase in the governance level produces an increase in the GDP per capita. The above explanation leads us to believe that there is a connection between the governance index and the value of the GDP per capita, and this is the conclusion that we may draw as a result. The rise in the governance index has a direct relationship to the rise in GDP per capita values, in which export value is also an important numerator.

Figure 2: Correlation between log value of export and governance indicator.

Source: Done in Stata based on above mentioned databases.

The relationship between export value and governance index can be seen in the scatter plot graph that was presented in Figure IV-3. The above graph was created by plotting the value of 105 nations' exports against their respective governance indices between the years 2001 and 2020. The log value of the exports index, which is described along the y axis, and the governance index, which is described along the x axis. According to the graph, the red line is demonstrating an upward trend, hence, we are able to state that an increase in the governance level produces an increase in the amount of export that occurs. Given the information presented above, it is reasonable to draw the conclusion that there is a connection between the governance index and the value of exports. The increase in the governance index can be directly correlated to the rise in export values.

Table 1: Estimating Governance Index with time and country fixed effect models.

Variables	Coefficients
Governance	0.516* (0.282)
Ln(GDP)	0.498*** (0.151)
Ln(Population)	1.281*** (0.407)

R-squared	0.840
Number of observations	2100

Note: *** indicates significance at the 1% level. ** indicates significance at the 5% level. * indicates significance at the 10% level. Robust standard errors are shown in parentheses.

Source: Done in Stata based on above mentioned databases.

The explanatory variables account for more than 84 percent of the observed variation in export in the data, as indicated by the model's R squared of 0.84. The most important one in this table is the average of all six governance indicators, which is statistically significant at the 10% level and has a positive coefficient. For instance, a 1% increase in the governance index will result in a 0.52% increase in export value. When we look at the GDP term, we can see that log export is positively correlated with the log form of GDP, which is consistent with what we would anticipate given that a 1% increase in GDP tends to increase export value by about 0.50 percent. It is statistically significant at the 1% level. Population is statistically significant at the 1% level and has a positive coefficient. A 1% increase in population will result in a 1.28% increase in export value.

The findings of this study have important implications for policymakers in Uzbekistan. To increase the country's export value, the government should focus on improving governance. The government needs to create a more transparent and accountable system by reducing bureaucratic barriers to trade and enhancing transparency and accountability in public procurement processes.

In conclusion, the study provides evidence that governance has a significant impact on the export value of Uzbekistan. The findings suggest that improving governance, promoting private sector development, and enhancing trade competitiveness are essential for increasing export value and promoting sustainable economic growth and development in Uzbekistan.

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. Improve governance:
2. Strengthen institutional capacity:
3. Promote private sector development:
4. Enhance trade competitiveness:
5. Monitor and evaluate progress:

Overall, these recommendations could help Uzbekistan to improve its governance and increase its export value, contributing to sustainable economic development and growth.

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